

Staged Dialogue between a Scientist and a Playwright

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Introduction

This short staged dialogue explores the interaction between science and art, between logic and intuition. It is inspired by a song from Divokej Bill and the play 'Garden Party' by Václav Havel.

Prelude

It happened that today I heard a well-known song by the band Divokej Bill. When I heard the words: "The world is cruel, it won't come back," I was inspired to write a short theatrical drama.

Dialogue

A scientist Miloš and a playwright Václav meet in a garden. Miloš orders a coffee. Václav orders a beer and lights a cigarette.

Miloš: So, Vašek, imagine what happened to me. I was at a meeting with the chairman.

Václav: Go on, I'm interested. (Takes a drag from his cigarette and sips his beer.)

Miloš: He came in wearing a starched shirt, a shiny tie, and a polished jacket. Then there was a speech. Everyone applauded.

Václav: So what?

Miloš: There was this one gentleman. We stood by a table; I was talking. He just said, "You'll get somewhere." Then he went for food. I didn't get it.

Václav: He's already done with everything. He doesn't need anything. He knows when to applaud, when to smile... You get it? (Takes a sip and a drag.)

Miloš: But! There were young students standing alone at a table. So I started talking. And suddenly, we thought we would be alone here. And I said, "That's alright." I know that feeling; it happened to me too. One of them went out for a smoke with me. I asked, "How was the speech?" Just something like... "It's nice..." You get it?

Václav: Of course! Didn't you get it? (Smiles.)

Miloš: It's like some dumb play. Havel's Garden Party?

Václav: (Smiles, taps out his cigarette, and finishes his beer in one gulp.)

Miloš: What should I do?

Václav: Do nothing... (Smiles.) Just go where you don't have to watch it all.

Miloš: Aha! That's it! I expected the chairman among the people?

Václav: You're Hugo, aren't you? (Smiles.)

Miloš finishes his coffee and orders a beer... the dialogue continues with a cheerful conversation about life.

Conclusion

This dialogue highlights the balance between rationality and emotion, science and art. It shows how intuition can guide logic, and how true understanding requires both.

How do you create? I don't know about you, but intuition always guides me. Science can be an art too.